

Digital Signature and Watermark Methods For Image Authentication using Cryptography Analysis

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Abstract

The digital signature and watermarking methods are used for image authentication. Digital signature encodes the signature in a file separate from the original image. Cryptographic algorithms have suggested several advantages over the traditional encryption algorithms such as high security, speed, reasonable computational overheads and computational power. A digital watermark and signature method for image authentication using cryptography analysis is proposed. The digital signature created for the original image and apply watermark. Images are resized before transmission in the network. After digital signature and water marking an image, apply the encryption and decryption process to an image for the authentication. The encryption is used to securely transmit data in open networks for the encryption of an image using public key and decrypt that image using private key.

Keywords: Digital Signature, Water Marking, Cryptography, Authentication, security

1. Introduction

1.1 Digital Signature

Digital signature is a sort of Cryptography. Cryptography means keeping communications private. Its mainly used for the converting of the information is encryption and decryption. No one can't access the information without access key.

The main process of the digital signature is similarly as the handwritten signature. its like paper signature and it having the digital certificate using this verifies the identity.

1.2 Watermarking

Watermarking is a sub-discipline of information hiding. It is the process of embedding information into a digital signal in a way that is difficult to remove. It's providing copyright protection for intellectual method that's in digital format.

1.3 Cryptography

The cryptography is providing better mechanisms for information security. In this analysis to provide the public and private keys for recovery the original information. The ability store and transfer sensitive information. By using the different encryption methods for generating public keys, decryption using for private keys.

This method applied to digital signatures and watermarking for to provide high security in transactions.

2. Literature Survey

2.1 “Digital Signature and Digital Watermark Scheme for Image Authentication”

This paper is investigate the combination of digital signature and watermarking is applied a host image for authentication process. The original images are having the water mark and apply the digital signature on it before the transmission in the internet.

2.2 “A New Algorithm of Encryption and Decryption of Images Using Chaotic Mapping”

The combination of chaotic theory and cryptography forms an important field of information security. In this paper implement encryption and decryption using chaotic mapping applying plain-image.

2.3“Image Encryption Using Block-Based Transformation Algorithm”

Encryption is used to securely transmit data in open networks. In this paper developed for the confidential image data from unauthorized access. The original images was divided into sub images and apply the transformation algorithms for better security.

3. Methodologies

3.1 Digital signature and Watermarking

Digital signature is a sort of Cryptography. Cryptography means keeping communications private. It deals with encryption, decryption and authentication.

3.1.1. Secret key or Symmetric Cryptography

In this processes sender and receiver messages have to know the similarly key for encryption and decryption of a message.

3.1.2 Public key or Asymmetric Cryptography

Asymmetric Cryptography involves two related keys, one of which only the the private key and the other 'public key.

3.1.3 Creation of Digital Signature

The creation of digital signature is done by getting the details from administrator, and the created signature is posted to the signature table and this is used by the certification authority. This is done by the certification authority and creates a personal identification to the person. This is carried out by using the **Digital Signature** Algorithm and the **Secure Hashing** algorithm. This digital signature provides a personalization.

Fig 3.1.1: Using the SHA with the DSA

3.1.4 Digital Signature Algorithm

(i) **GLOBAL PUBLIC-KEY COMPONENTS**

1. $p =$ a prime number, where $2^{L-1} < p < 2^L$ for $512 = < L = <1024$ and L a multiple of 64
2. $q =$ a prime divisor of $p - 1$, where $2^{159} < q < 2^{160}$
3. $g = h^{(p-1)/q} \bmod p$, where h is any integer with $1 < h < p - 1$ such that $h^{(p-1)/q} \bmod P > 1$ (g has order $q \bmod p$).

(ii) **THE USER'S PRIVATE KEY:**

$x =$ a randomly or pseudo randomly generated integer with $0 < x < q$

(iii) **USER'S PUBLIC KEY:**

$$y = g^x \bmod p$$

(iv) **USER'S PER-MESSAGE SECRET NUMBER:**

$k =$ a randomly or pseudo randomly generated integer with $0 < k < q$

3.2. Watermarking Digital Signature

Digital image watermarking schemes mainly fall into two broad categories:

3.2.1 Spatial-domain techniques

The spatial –domain techniques consist of two categories, these are

a) Least-Significant Bit (LSB): The given image contains pixels these pixels are indicated by the 8-bit sequence, the watermarks are linked two the last, bit of selected pixels of the original image. its used to hide the information and attackers could not destroy the information.

b) SSM-Modulation-Based Technique: These technique are applied in the water marking algorithms with an linked information and attached to the original image with pseudo noise signal ,its modulated by the watermark.

3.2.2 Frequency-domain techniques

The frequency-domain techniques mainly used for watermarking of the human visual system are better captured by the spectral coefficients.

The transforms are broadly categorized in two ways

(a) Discrete Cosine Transformation (DCT)

(b) Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT)

The following figures are explained about Discrete Cosine Transformation and Discrete Wavelet Transformation.

Fig: 3.2.2.1 One Level DWT

Original Image

Water Marked Imag

Fig: 3.2.2 .2 Two Level DWT

Original Image

Water Marked Image

Fig: 3.2.2.4 Three Levels DWT

The above process of 2-D discrete wavelet transforms are divided into three sub images for providing the watermarking for host image.

3.2.3 Authentication using image verification

This is done by authentication verifier, initially he logins with person date of birth and passport/driving license information and extracts the signature, and these details are submitted for the verification process. By this image verification is done and can know the details.

4. Cryptography

An encryption system is also called a cipher, or a cryptosystem. The message consists of plaintext, and cipher text. Denote the plaintext and the cipher text by P and C, respectively. The encryption procedure of a cipher can be described as $C = E_{K_e}(P)$, where K_e is the encryption key and E is the encryption function. Similarly, the decryption procedure is $P = D_{K_d}(C)$, where K_d is the decryption key and D is the decryption function. For public-key ciphers, the encryption key K_e is published, and the decryption key K_d is kept private, for which no additional secret channel is needed for key transfer.

Fig: 4.1 Encryption and Decryption

5. Experimental Results

5.1 Water Marking

The given picture shows the watermarking in the bottom at left corner

Figure 5.1.1 watermarking

5.2 Watermarking as digital signature

The given picture shows the watermarking with digital signature in the bottom at left corner

Fig 5.2.1 watermarking as digital signature

5.3 Encryption for image

The given picture shows the encryption for image

Fig: 5.3.1 Encryption

5.4 Decryption for image

The given picture shows the decryption for image

Fig: 5.4.1 Decryption

6. Conclusion

Digital signature and watermark are two techniques used for copyright protection and authentication, respectively. In this paper a digital signature and watermark methods are used cryptography analysis proposed for image security. Experiments show our scheme is robust to reasonable compression rate while preserving good image quality, and capable to authentication.

7. Future Work

Future work will be focused on more robust signature extraction method and possible ways to recover the illegally modified image without the original image.

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